

Resting Calcium Dependence of the Outer Hair Cell Hair Bundle

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Abstract. The hair bundles of outer hair cells (OHCs) are required for the high sensitivity, sharp-tuning, and large dynamic range of hearing. The hair bundle's ion channels are, however, not fully closed at rest (i.e., in the absence of stimulus forces) - there is experimental evidence that the receptor current at rest is around 50 percent of its maximum value in endolymphatic conditions (0.02 mM calcium), whereas in perilymphatic conditions (1.5 mM calcium) it is around 8 percent of its maximum value. Along with this change in resting receptor current, the resting bundle position shifts. The mechanisms responsible for the calcium dependence of the resting receptor current and the bundle position remain unclear. Intriguingly, additional experiments have shown that stereocilia possessing mechano-electrical transduction ion channels reduce in height when the calcium concentration is lowered. We hypothesize that stereocilium height reductions owing to lowering calcium concentration increases gating-spring tension. The increase in tension increases the resting current and decreases the resting bundle position. We test this hypothesis by building a computational model that accounts for the morphology (stereocilium heights, widths, and pivot positions) of the OHC hair bundle, which are assigned from published experimental data. We show that a decrease in stereocilium heights increases the resting receptor current from perilymph to endolymph. Along with the increase in receptor current, our model also predicts a decrease in the bundle resting position. In agreement with our hypothesis, we find that the tension in the gating-springs at rest in endolymph is higher than in perilymph. We show that a change in the heights of the ion channel containing stereocilia can explain the difference in resting receptor currents and resting bundle position at high and low calcium concentrations.

INTRODUCTION

Hair bundles are the mechanosensing organelles on the apical surface of hair cells, the sound receptors inside our ears. We focus on the hair bundles of outer hair cells, which comprise three rows of rod-like stereocilia linked by gating springs. Ion channels are located at the tips of the shorter stereocilia (Fig. 1). Sound-induced forces deflect the stereocilia, which in turn extends the gating springs and opens the ion channels. Consequently, a receptor current passes through the ion channels. A resting bundle (i.e. an unstimulated bundle) has an inward resting current [1, 2], indicating that the ion channels are not fully closed. The value of this resting current and the resting deflection depend on extracellular calcium concentration [2]. We propose a mechanism that explains how changing extracellular calcium changes the resting current and deflection. We use an experimentally-calibrated mathematical model to evaluate the feasibility of our proposal. In addition, we predict how the resting tension changes owing to changes in extracellular calcium.

METHODS

We use experimental data to calibrate a model of the outer-hair-cell hair bundle comprising three stereocilia, two gating springs and two ion channels (Fig. 1). The stereociliary heights and width are determined from published experimental data [2, 3]. The values of the spacings between rows are based on our unpublished experimental data. The physiological properties of the hair bundle are constrained by seven experimental observations reported previously (Table 1).

RESULTS

Using bundle morphology and force-balance conditions, we find that the resting displacement of the tip of the bundle with respect to the vertical is negative, which is consistent with prior observations [4]. We predict that a decrease of 10 nm in the heights of the transducing stereocilia when the calcium concentration is decreased increases the resting gating-spring tension from 17 pN to 32 pN. This increase in the gating-spring tension increases the resting receptor

Constraint	Experiment	Model
1. Bundle stiffness without gating springs	5.5 ± 2 mN/m [2]	5.5 mN/m
2. Bundle stiffness with gating springs	8.6 ± 2.3 mN/m [2]	8.6 mN/m
3. Resting tip-link length (0.05 mM calcium)	186 ± 38 nm [3]	186 nm
4. Resting current (1.5 mM calcium)	0.087 [1]	0.087
5. Resting current (0.02 mM calcium)	0.5 [1, 2]	0.5
6. Activation-curve width (0.27-0.73)	34 nm [1]	34.1 nm
7. Deflection from breaking gating springs	45 ± 10 nm [2]	45 nm

TABLE 1. Summary of constraints used to calibrate our model. Experimentally observed values and the values fitted by our model are shown.

current from 0.087 at high calcium concentrations to 0.5 at low calcium concentrations, and decreases the bundle resting position by 26 nm.

FIGURE 1. OHC bundle model Schematic representation of the outer-hair-cell hair bundle, consisting of three rows 1, 2 and 3 of decreasing heights. Gating springs (orange) link each stereocilium with its neighboring shorter stereocilium. The stereocilia in row 2 and row 3 have ion channels (blue) at their tips.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

We show that the experimentally observed dependence of the resting current and bundle deflection on calcium can be explained by a decrease in the heights of the row 2 and 3 stereocilia by only 10 nm in low calcium. Calcium-induced changes in row heights might be caused by calcium-dependent actin polymerization at the stereociliary tips [5]. Each actin monomer is around 7 nm in diameter and the polymerization rate at the stereociliary tips is around 1-10 monomers per second. This indicates that a change of 10 nm in the stereociliary heights would roughly require the addition of 1-2 monomers, which takes place in around 1 second.

Calcium-induced changes in the resting current and bundle deflection may also be caused by adaptation, the process which dynamically restores the mechanosensitivity of hair bundles in response to a sustained stimulus [6]. In experiments, adaptation manifests as a decay in the receptor current upon applying a sustained stimulus. This decay, in mammalian cochlear hair bundles, has a calcium-independent fast component (time scales around 1 ms) and a slow calcium-dependent component (time scale 10-100 ms) [7, 8].

The speed of the proposed height change is at present unknown and how the height change might be related to adaptation remains to be determined.

FIGURE 2. Mechanism for calcium dependence of the resting current and bundle deflection (A) A schematic representing a hair bundle in high calcium is shown. The resting current (red arrows), resting channels (dark blue elements), resting deflection from vertical (red dot), resting tensions (dark orange arrows), and heights of rows 2 and 3 (black arrows) are indicated. (B) A schematic representing a hair bundle in low calcium is shown. The resting current (pink arrows), resting channels (light blue elements), resting deflection from vertical (pink dot), resting tensions (light yellow arrows), and heights of row 2 and 3 (gray arrows) are indicated.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Ondrej Tichacek] : Dear Rayan, thank you for your nice paper regarding a very interesting topic! Here are some specific questions I have. The paper does not provide many details on the methodology. I am very curious about the physics/mathematics behind your model and calculations. Could you elaborate on this aspect?

[Rayan Chatterjee] : Our model hair bundle comprises three rows of stereocilia, two gating springs and two ion channels. Seven parameters define the locations of the two upper tip-link densities, the pivot stiffness of each stereocilium, the stiffness, unloaded length, and half-activation length of the gating springs, and the channel gating swing. Using bundle morphology and force-balance equations, we derive seven physical constraints, one from each experimental observation listed in Table 1. These constraints are used to determine the parameter values.

[Ondrej Tichacek] : Your results show a significant increase in gating-spring tension when calcium concentration is decreased. Could you elaborate on the biological mechanisms that might explain this increase in tension?

[Rayan Chatterjee] : We show that the increase in gating-spring tension at low extracellular calcium concentration can be caused by a reduction in the heights of rows 2 and 3. Several biological mechanisms can contribute to this reduction, e.g., actin polymerization at the tips of these rows, as suggested by Vélez Ortega et al., eLife (2017), or adaptation, which causes a decrease in the receptor current when the bundle is subjected to a sustained stimulus.

[Ondrej Tichacek] : How did you estimate the tension increase?

[Rayan Chatterjee] : After determining the parameter values from the experimental constraints, we calculated the resting tension from the equations describing the bundle at rest. To account for the difference in resting current in high and low calcium, we changed the heights of rows 2 and 3. These height changes caused the resting tension to increase in low calcium.

[Ondrej Tichacek] : Could you please clarify what you mean by "negative" displacement of the tip of the bundle?

[Rayan Chatterjee] : Positive displacements are defined to be toward the tallest stereocilium row (row 1) (Figs. 1 and 2). Zero displacement corresponds to a vertical stereocilium. Correspondingly, the tip-displacement is negative if row 1 is not vertical and is displaced toward row 3.

[Ondrej Tichacek] : If both the 2nd and 3rd row stereocilia decrease their length equally, only the spring between the 2nd and 1st row should be affected. Is that correct? Did you account for that in your calculations?

[Rayan Chatterjee] : No, this is not correct. Each gating spring links the apex of one stereocilium to the body of its neighboring, higher stereocilium. The attachment point on the higher stereocilium, known as the upper tip-link density, is located below the stereociliary tip and is not affected by the height changes predicted from our model. A decrease in the heights of both rows 2 and 3 increases the resting tensions. In our model, we allow the changes in the heights of rows 2 and 3 to be different. The approximately-equal length changes observed is a prediction of the model.

[Ondrej Tichacek] : I understand you were focusing on the characteristic perilymph/endolymph calcium concentrations. I would be curious to know the profile of row height change for different concentrations. Do you know if such data exist?

[Rayan Chatterjee] : Vélez Ortega et al., eLife (2017) reports the decrease in lengths of rows 2 and 3 upon reducing the extracellular calcium concentration.

[Varun Goyal] : Hi Dr. Chatterjee and Dr. Ó Maoiléidigh, Exciting work! Short, to the point, and descriptive. I had only one question about the speed at which such a length change would occur, but as you have mentioned, it is currently unknown, including its dependence on adaptation. It made me think about two contrasting points: Since fast adaptation is calcium-independent, if at all length change depends on adaptation, it should be the slow adaptation, right? Or because those calcium changes are extracellular and at rest, stereociliary length changes could still be altered by fast adaptation? Just curious about what your opinions are on this or if it is inconclusive at this point. Looking forward to meeting you at MoH.

[Rayan Chatterjee] : We are inconclusive about the time scales associated with the height change that we propose. Thus, both fast and slow adaptation can in principle be attributed to the height change.

[Varun Goyal] : PS: In the Fig 1 caption, there is just a small typo in the third line, "rows 2 and row 3".

[Rayan Chatterjee] : Thanks for pointing this out.

[Jamis McGrath] : Drs. Chatterjee and Ó Maoiléidigh, the manuscript describes a model of the mammalian outer hair cell bundle using three stereocilia, two gating springs, and two channels. The authors use this model to determine that decreased stereocilia lengths in the shorter rows (10 nm) could explain the dependence of resting current and

bundle deflection on calcium. A mechanism is posited in which dynamic actin regulation at stereocilia tips could provide the necessary length changes. The methods section should be expanded to include more information about generating the model. I am not very familiar with research using computational modeling, so it may be normal to include the current level of detail. I think the methods should include enough information to give the reader a sense of how the work was done.

[Rayan Chatterjee] : As you have rightly pointed out, our model hair bundle comprises three rows of stereocilia, two gating springs and two ion channels. The heights and width of the stereocilia, the spacing between the rows 1 and 2 and between 2 and 3 are taken from experimental observations. The parameters characterizing the model bundle are the locations of the upper tip-link densities, the pivot stiffness of the stereocilia, the stiffness and unloaded length of the gating-spring, the channel gating swing, and the half-activation length of the gating springs. We adjust these parameters so that the model bundle response matches the experimental observations listed in Table 1.

[Jamis McGrath] : Regarding the discussion, consider how other proteins influence actin polymerization. For example, formins, the local and available actin population, crosslinkers, severing and capping proteins, and more partners catalyze actin filament elongation and disassembly. Many of these actin regulators are present and specialized at the stereocilia tips and are distinct between stereocilia presumed to contain mechanotransducing channels (shorter rows) versus those without that channel activity. It is also worth noting that this does not need to be independent of adaptation and, in particular, the slower component of the process could be driven by actin regulation, at least in part. For the figures, I would add a legend based on the colors of indicating arrows in figure 2. The change in colors between A and B was very confusing. The dots above the stereocilia was very helpful in defining “bundle position”. I will email you a copy of the manuscripts containing my edits in case they are helpful.

[Rayan Chatterjee] : Thanks for the suggestions. A detailed analysis of the types of polymerization which can cause the height change is beyond the scope of this work. The legends for arrows and dots in Fig.2 are described in the caption.